

Investigating The Conflict Between Child Human Rights and Child Disciplinary Practices in the Family Institutions of Northern Province' Mporokoso Township

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Abstract – The focus of this study was to investigate the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions of Mporokoso Township. The study endeavored to address the following objectives: To verify the presence of the conflict, to describe the actual conflict experienced, to explore effects of the conflict and to suggest possible ways of how the conflict can be resolved. A qualitative case study design was used to gather data for this research. Data was gathered using structured and focused group interviews/discussions. This research study was guided by conflict theory. Research participants included Human Rights Commission of Zambia, Parents/guardians, Children and Police Officers from Victim Support Unit. The following are the main research findings revealed by the study: Beatings versus child protection from physical or emotional abuse, right to quality health care and nurturing versus neglect and abandonment which leads to archaic uncontrolled behavior, right to shelter versus no or poor shelter, right to education versus no or poor education, right to security and social protection by both parents and state agents versus physical injuries and deformities, child right to participate in community programs for themselves versus denied freedom of community participation and programs for themselves. It was also revealed that, there was misunderstanding and hatred between children and their parents/guardians. The conflict also leads to the fear by parents for prosecution by their own children. It was also revealed that there are poor government policies on both child rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions. The study concluded that, the most common form of discipline was physical abuse followed by verbal abuse which is an infringement on the part of child rights. Children are used as tools of labor and undergo many abuses as there is no security and social protection, and commitment to fulfill children's rights by child rights duty bearers. It was also concluded that, the conflict can be resolved by formulating policies that promote, protect and fulfill child rights.

Keywords – Conflict; Child; Human Rights; Disciplinary Practices; Family Institution.

I. INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides the background information to the study. It further presents the definition of the key concepts, problem statement, research objectives (both main and specific objectives), the research questions and the significance of the study.

The study aimed at exploration of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institution in Zambia. The research proposes to answer the following questions: Whether there is a conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institution in Mporokoso Township? What kind of conflict is experienced? What are the effects of the conflict? And finally, what should be done to resolve the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions in Zambia?

Background of the Study

A long time ago there were no special protections given to children. In the Middle-Age, children were considered as small adults. Older children were expected to swiftly adopt adult tasks and accountabilities, to meet the strict necessities of daily life. Further, harsh punishments for minor violations were common. Beatings and other forms of physical discipline occurred regularly; one legislator even suggested capital punishment for children's misbehavior (Orme, 2008).

The use of physical punishment practices was used as a disciplinary action taken to shape behavior, not a pervasive dispensing of beatings for no reason. Corporal punishment was undoubtedly the norm. Therefore, there was need to change this norm as it had negative effects on the child in their adulthood.

Many parents continue to use physical punishment to discipline their children for various reasons. The most common reason is the belief that if parents truly love their children and care about their well-being then, they must impose their authority, values and cultural beliefs on them. This belief is based on the fear of spoiling a child. However, later with the coming of human rights, such notion was being discouraged as physical discipline was said to be cruel to humanity. One of the unknown scholars said, "If you strike an animal it's called cruelty, if you strike an adult it is called assault, but if you strike a child it's called discipline, (Ibid)." Despite human rights advocacy, child discipline through physical punishment is still a common aspect of society (Murray, etal. 2006).

Statement of the Problem

In 1968 Zambia adopted international conventions on children's rights (UN Report, 2001). This led to the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Zambia. In Zambian context children have been raised by physical punishment when disciplining the child and this is well backed by Zambian tradition and culture as an acceptable disciplinary practice. However child rising in Zambia, conflict with certain child

human rights making it very difficult to discipline the children in Zambian situation, because when this happens, children complain that their human rights are violated and in the course of discipline, the disciplinarian may be arrested for inhuman treatment or assaulting. Despite the existence of this conflict since 1968 when Zambia adopted international conventions on child human rights, not much has been done to investigate the nature of this conflict hence the need to do so particularly in Mporokoso Township.

Objectives of the study

1. To verify the presence of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township.
2. To describe the actual conflict experienced between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions in Mporokosotownship.
3. To explore effects of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions in Mporokosotownship.
4. To suggest possible ways of how the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokosotownship can be resolved.

Significance of the Study

This study is rationalized for a number of reasons. Firstly, the study is relevant as it may generate new knowledge that may contribute to the existing body of knowledge with regard to the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions. Secondly, the study is important as it may help in filling the gaps in the existing body of knowledge on the role of stakeholders in overcoming the conflict. The findings of the study may also contribute to knowledge through bringing to the fore the effects of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions in Mporokosotownship and Zambia at large. To that effect, the study is significant because it may contribute to limited empirical literature in regard to the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions. Additionally, the study may provide factual data that will add to the growing discourse of conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

This chapter presents the relevant literatures or studies that were previously conducted on this subject. It discusses literature related to conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institution. It particularly focuses on basic facts of child discipline in homes, effects of child rights/parental discipline and the conflict between child human rights and parents/caregivers. Most of these studies aimed at exploring the conflict between the child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family, among which a number of them have shown a considerable correlation between home affairs issues and legal matters (Ormen, 2007). The

literature review further focus on a general perspective, on a global front (parts of America, Europe and African) as well as local perspective in the Zambian society. To sum up the study, a research gap has been identified as not much research has been done on child rights and disciplinary practices in family institutions in Zambia and hence the need for this research. The literature reviewed in this research has been sourced from credible source such as books, journals, national and international newspapers sources that cover in the Zambian society, government publications and the other academic journals to ensure that the process of gap analysis is founded on a comprehensive, valid, sound and reliable set of data. This study has focused on most recent studies and publications to ensure the data used in the study represents the most recent situation as far as child rights and disciplinary practices in family institutions in the Zambian society is concerned.

Firstly, there is need to understand child rights in a more detailed manner. Child Rights have been mentioned above a few times. Child Human Rights- Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) (1989), defines a child as "any human being below the age of eighteen years. Children's rights are also defined in a wide spectrum of economic, civil, political and social rights. Children's rights take into account the necessity of development of the child. According to Ginsburg et. al.,(2009). As a vulnerable group, children have particular rights that recognize their special need for protection and help them develop their full potential, It is every child's right to have a say on the things that affects their life. However, some children are either too young to make solid decisions. Children are not helpless objects of charity or a property of their parents. They are recognized as human beings and the subjects of their own rights. A child is an individual, a family and community member with rights. Children should enjoy the basic qualities of life as rights rather than privileges accorded to (CRC, 2006).

All child disciplinary practices in a home can legitimately be described as good in view of parents/caregivers. Some of common African child disciplinary practices in a family institution are canning the child, beatings, pulling hair or ears, yelling, kicking, burning fingers, flogging, denying the child food. In addition, some of the examples of undesirable practices in Africa are birth superstitions, male circumcision (mukanda), corporal punishment, cosmetic mutilation, cursing, dowry and bride price, food taboos, withholding food / starvation, child marriage, marriage by abduction (elopement), menstruation exclusion, organ removal, educative sex (rape), Sex teaching (Nkolola), and virginity testing among others. Child human rights and child disciplinary practices in home institutions clearly shows this gap and the conflict that are being exhibited between the two rights.

Brady (2015) conducted a study on the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in home institutions. The study was conducted in Afghanistan. The findings of the study revealed that the conflict between child rights and child disciplinary practices in home

institutions accounted for 48%. The findings further showed that the conflict had increased from 17% in 2009 to 28.2% in 2011. Similarly, a study by George revealed that the presence of conflict in Bangladesh accounted for 21% (George, 2014). However, the above study which was conducted by Brady and George is limited. Moreover, the study did not indicate a detailed prevalence of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions. In this regard, it is important to conduct the study of this nature to fill these gaps.

Another similar study was conducted by Muhammad in 2007 in Zambia. The study investigated the prevalence of child disciplinary practices at home. The findings of the study showed that child disciplinary practices accounted for 41.3%. It was further noted that the child disciplinary practices were high in rural areas at 27% compared to urban parts of the country where it accounted for 13.2%. However, the above study conducted by Muhammad is limited for a number of reasons. Firstly, the study did not specifically investigate the presence of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in home institutions. It sort to investigate the prevalence of child disciplinary practices at home which is contrary to the researcher's current topic. Secondly, the study did not specify the exactly place where the study was conducted (Muhammad, 2007).

Clachert (2014), show the actual conflict experienced between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions. He observed that parents fail to discipline their children because of the human rights which were the actual conflict. It was also observed that misbehavior of the children in the name of human rights is where real conflict is experienced, (Clachert, 2014) The study by Hatton (2015), however is also limited as it did not clearly indicate the actual conflict experienced. The study just provides crucial insights into potential conflicts. To that effect, it is vital to conduct the researchers current study in order to specifically assess the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions.

According to Brady et.al. (2009), child discipline includes training directed at developing the judgment, behavioral boundaries, self-control, self-sufficiency and positive ethical social conduct in children. Therefore, child disciplinary practices are vital as they have broad implications in the child's well-being, and appropriate discipline is viewed as being a necessary part of child rearing. Further, the study of child disciplinary practices in a multicultural context is broad, as culture and care giving interact to influence children's development and their experience of developmental stages (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1990). Africa's capacity to translate this understanding into changing norms and behaviors has lagged behind, in part due to the lack of cross-cultural research. Traditionally, in Africa a child as early as 3 years, is expected to do a lot of works and this include Goat and Cattle rearing, field ploughing, harvesting, taking care of siblings, cooking and serving adults and many other

activities especially in rural parts of African countries. According to the human rights organizations this is a direct conflict to human rights of the children. Until recent times in the late 1980s corporal punishment still strived in African homes and institution of learning especially in primary and secondary schools. It is until recent years that most African countries, Zambia inclusive became signatories of United Nation Child Human Rights Convention.

There are challenges faced by parents in teaching children how to behave in a socially responsible manner. Discipline is important for all children and it is through discipline that children internalize the rules, values, and beliefs that help them become respectful and contributing members of society positively however, the United Nation Convention on the Rights of the Child does not specifically address what type of discipline parents should use. The convention and social science data are in agreement with the use of a non-violent method that is, non-physical discipline. This is in the best interest of the healthy development of the child. Unfortunately, nation's laws that of many countries, continues to allow for the use of physical punishment with children (Katherine, 2017).

In summary this chapter presented relevant literatures and studies that were previously conducted on this subject. It discussed literature related to conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institution. It particularly focused on basic facts of child discipline in homes, effects of child rights/parental discipline and the conflict between child human rights and parents/caregivers. Most of these studies aimed at exploring the conflict between the child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family, among which a number of them revealed a considerable correlation between home affairs issues and legal matters. The literature review further focused on a global front (parts of America, Europe and African) as well as local perspective in the Zambian society. A research gap has been identified as not much research has been done on child rights and disciplinary practices in family institutions in Zambia and hence the need for this research.

III. METHODOLOGY

A qualitative research approach was used in this study. Saunders and Lewis (2016), define qualitative approach as the approach usually associated with the social constructivist paradigm which emphasis the social constructed nature of reality. It is about recording, analyzing and attempting to uncover the deeper meaning and significance of human behaviors and experience, including contradicting beliefs, behaviors and emotions (Lewis, 2015). Researchers are interested in gaining a rich and complex understanding of people's experience and not in obtaining the information which can be generalized to other larger groups. To that effect therefore this approach was used as it enabled the researcher to gain complex understanding of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions from

people’s point of view. Furthermore, the approach helped the researcher to collect rich information regarding the issue under investigation as there was little data on this subject.

Research Design

The study used a case study research design to assess the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in families in Mporokoso Township. Case study was adopted because the current study focused on specific area (Mporokoso Township) which was intended to evaluate in-depth interviews. Gulsecen&Kubat (2014), assert that Case study design allows the exploration and understanding of complex issues. It is a robust research design particularly used when a holistic, in-depth investigation is required. Through case study methods, a researcher is able to understand the behavioral conditions through the actor’s perspective. Descriptive survey has been used hence the study was a qualitative study, which helped explain both the process and outcome of a phenomenon through complete interviews and to some extent observation, reconstruction of sentences or thoughts, and analysis of the cases under investigation (Telis, 2015). Case studies are characterized by exploratory study and an interpretative paradigm, which emphasizes subjective experiences they have for an individual. Therefore, the subjective views of a researcher on a particular situation play a vital part in the study results (Vogrin, 2013:14). Another characteristic of qualitative research design is its idiographic approach, which emphasizes an individual’s perspective on the investigative situation, process and relations.

Sample Size

The aim of this study was to generate in-depth information on the conflict between child human rights and the child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township. Therefore, the sample consisted of 31 participants; two (2) human rights activists, 14 parents, 3 police officers and 12 children. These were sampled on the basis of their knowledge about the conflict between child human rights and the child disciplinary practices in family institutions. According to Mohan (2003), sample sizes in qualitative research should not be too large as it may be difficult for the researcher to extract thick and in-depth data. Therefore, this sample size was appropriate for easy analysis of data as well as for gathering detailed information regarding the issue under study.

Data Analysis

The data was systematically analyzed using qualitative thematic analysis. Thematic content analysis was used as a method for analyzing qualitative data (Lippincott, 2012 cited by Chanda, 2014). This involves content analysis to extract the meanings of the transcriptions of recorded or written interviews. In researcher’s current study the data was firstly read and reread in order to be familiar with what the data entails. Secondly, the initial codes that have reoccurring patterns were generated in order to gain meaningful of data as it related to the research questions. Thereafter, data was coded into conceptual categories of similar meaning. This is called meaning categorization according to Edmonds (2015). Thirdly, themes were

searched. This enabled the researcher to examine how codes combine to form overarching themes in the data. At this point, the researcher had a list of themes and his focus was on broader themes in the data. The researcher also narrowed down the potential themes into main themes in order to allow categories of data to emerge. Fourthly, themes were refined and reviewed to see if they are connected between overlapping themes. Themes were then be defined and named and helped the researcher in analyzing data within each theme. Lastly, the researcher decided which themes make meaningful understanding of the main concerns of the research. Chapter four (4) will follow and amplify this chapter.

IV. PRESENTATION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

Introduction

The chapter presents research findings of the study. The research findings are presented in line with the research objective of the study. Specifically the chapter focuses on presenting findings from semi-structured interviews and focused group discussions respectively. All the findings presented in this chapter are grounded in the overall aim of the entire study which is to investigate the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township.

Gender of the Respondents

The tables below indicate gender balance of the study participants-fourteen (14) females, and seventeen (17) males representing 45% females and 54.8% male respondent.

Table 1

Gender	M 17	F 14
sex	54.8%	45.1%

Age and Sex Distribution of Children

Age & Sex Distribution of Children	mal e	percenta ge	Fema le	Percenta ge	grad e
Age	mal e	percenta ge	Fema le	Percenta ge	grad e
14-17	14-17	41.6	2	16.16	11-12
10-14	2	16.6	3	25	8-10
Total	7	58.3	5	41.6	
Grand Total	12		38.7		

Age, Sex Distribution and Level of Education of Parents, HRA & Police Officers

Adult respondents include parents, Human rights activists, and the police officers. Age, sex and percentage were considered making a total of 18 representing 58% of the total participant. The breakdowns are as follows: Males-

35.7% were aged between 36 to 45 years, 14.2% were between 46 to 55 years as well as above 56 years respectively. Females – 33.3 were aged between 36 to 45 years, 14.2% were aged 14.2% were between 46 to 55 years and 5.5% were aged above 56 years.

Symbols used for the Sources of Data

The report also indicates symbols (codes) and data distribution for the study collected from a total of thirty-one (31) respondents. Naturally it is good to make a note of each one of the subsequent participants; two (2) Human Rights commission (HRA) came from Human Rights commission of Zambia; One (1) Police Officer (PO) is at the provincial level at victim support unity (VSU) and the other two (2) were Officers at a local police station under VSU in Mporokoso and the researcher had one on one interviews. FGD one (1) were pupils and residents of the target area in Mporokoso Township where focus group discussion interviews (8 pupils) were conducted at a high school and FGD two (2) had four (4) children were at a local church within Mporokoso. Fourteen (14) parent (P) participants came from the same target area. The P coded as parents, the researcher had one on one interviews.

Findings from Focused group discussion interviews

In relation with the objective above, the study confirmed the presence of conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township. The research study revealed the presence of conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions. This conflict existed at two main levels. These are: Beatings versus child protection from physical or emotional abuse and child submissiveness versus the right to freedom of speech and thought. Further, the research revealed that the conflict does exist especially that Zambia lacks clear guideline on how someone should discipline a child in Zambian society and Mporokoso Township is not an exception.

Findings Linked to Objective Four: ‘

To Suggest Possible Ways of how the Conflict between Child Human Rights and Child Disciplinary Practices can be Resolved in the Family Institutions in MporokosoTownship’. The study in line with the fourth objective revealed six findings. These are: Poor or no government policies and laws, no protection to fulfill children’s rights by child rights duty bearers, freedom of expression versus lack freedom to participate in programs for themselves duty bearers, Government does not work with civil society organization (CSO), no child rights in general school curriculum, parents are not sensitized or educated on the importance of human rights and no clear disciplinary practices between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions. In support of the above findings, in the focus

The Verification of the Presence of the Conflict between Child Human Rights and Child Disciplinary Practices in Family Institutions in MporokosoTownship To verify the presence of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in MporokosoTownship, the study revealed the presence of conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions. This conflict exists at two main levels. These are: Beatings versus child protection from physical or emotional abuse and child submissiveness versus the right to freedom of speech and thought. Further, the research revealed that the conflict does exist especially that Zambia lacks a clear guideline on how someone should discipline a child in the Zambian society and Mporokoso Township is not an exception. One of the reasons the conflict exists as revealed by the research study is because of traditions and cultural beliefs that has existed for a long time in Zambia.

According to the Declaration of the Rights of the Child in Geneva 1924, the United Nation Convention in agreement with what parents said above, the convention does not specifically address the type of discipline parents should use to discipline the children. The conventions on child human rights are in agreement with the use of non-violent methods which are nonphysical disciplinary practices. This is in the best interest of the healthy development of a child. Katherine (2017), points out that unfortunately, Zambian national laws, continue to allow use of physical punishment to discipline a child against international human rights principles and standards which prohibit any form of physical violence and disciplinary practices against children. Katherine (2017), also agrees with some of the respondent in this study that Zambia lacks clear guidelines on how parents should discipline their children.

The study described the actual conflict experienced between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in home institutions in MporokosoTownship. The findings of the study revealed that, the conflict is complex in that it is multi-faceted. In view of the forgoing, the findings of the study revealed that the conflict involves: disciplinary practices within the family which infringe on child rights, that is, the right to childhood social protection versus the home chores given to children, adequate standard of living versus lack of shelter, right to be loved and cared for by both parents versus child labor and sexual abuse, provision of security and social protection versus cruelty or inhuman treatment, freedom of choice versus forced child marriage, right to food versus starvation/poverty, right to quality health care and nurturing versus neglect and abandonment, and right to life versus death at a tender age.

Moreover, human rights respect the dignity and wellbeing of the child while the home disciplinary practices believe in giving extra hard work through home chores as a way of disciplining a child. Human rights promote childhood social protection as advanced by Clachert, et.al. (2005), in their study entitled „Zambian Children’s Experience of Corporal and Humiliating Punishment.“ They observed that parents fail to discipline their children because of human rights

V. DISCUSSION OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

which are a source of the actual conflict. Their study also revealed that, misbehavior of children in the name of human rights is where actual conflict is experienced. They further observed that, children are not well nurtured and cared for by their parents. Children undergo bizarre discipline such as deprivation of food and they are badly whipped or burnt. They may not be taken for health care services even when they are sick from beatings and sometimes are chased away from homes. Once chased from their homes, children suffer and experience all sorts of abuse from fellow children as well as adults which include: child labor, sexual abuse, and child marriage.

The findings in the current research study are also supported by Chikalanga (2013), who observed that the actual conflict can be seen in the area where guardians or any caregiver find it difficult to discipline their children because of human rights. In this regard, children refuse to listen to their parents because they feel they have their own rights that support them. However, Chakalanga (2013), strongly disputes the disciplinary actions taken by parents. He does not approve chasing the child away from home, cruel and inhuman treatment, deprivation/starvation of a child, instead, he advocates that children should be loved and cared for by both parents given good nutrition rich food and provided with quality health care services. He further urges that the child did not bring himself/herself to life and therefore, the giver of life should take responsibility to care for that which he/she brought forth to life (Chikalanga, 2013). His study however, is silent on some of the findings this research has revealed, such as child abuse from labor, sexual abuse, sex testing, child marriage and circumcision. The study explored effects of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions in Mporokoso Township. In line with the research objective above, the study revealed 85% of all the respondents acknowledged the effects of the conflict. The study findings revealed more complex effects of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions in Mporokoso Township. The conflict leads to the fear by parents to be taken to police for prosecution by their own children.

The conflict further leads to the abandonment of children. Major research findings revealed by the current study are: right to freedom of expression and thought versus verbal assault, right to associate with both parents versus neglect and abandonment, right to shelter versus no/poor shelter, right to care and good health versus poor health and lack of care, right to education versus no/poor education, right to security and social protection by both parents and state agents versus physical injuries and deformities, right to participate in community programs for themselves versus denied freedom of community participation and programs for themselves, right to playing and entertainment versus denied freedom to play and entertainment. There are other study research findings revealed in this current study.

In line with the fourth objective, the study revealed six findings. These are: Poor or no government policies and laws on child rights, there is no protection and commitment

to fulfill children's rights by child rights duty bearers (Human Rights Activists and other state agents), no freedom of expression for children to participate in programs for themselves, Government does not collaborate and work with Civil Society Organization (CSO) to curb or regulate child disciplinary practices in homes and try to promote child rights, there are no child rights in general school education curriculum put for the children to learn and know their rights, parents are not sensitized or educated on the importance of human rights and no clear disciplinary practices between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in the family institutions. The study investigated the possible ways of how the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices can be resolved. The findings of the study revealed that the conflict can be resolved by formulating policies and laws that promote, protect and fulfill child rights. In this regard therefore, the participants suggested that, the Zambian government must initiate policies, programs and laws that are designed to promote, protect and fulfill children's rights if the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices is to be addressed.

VI. CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

In conclusion this study sought to investigate the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township. The study specifically set out to verify the presence of the conflict, describe the actual conflict experienced, explored effects of the conflict and suggested possible ways of how the conflict can be resolved in Mporokoso Township. It can be concluded that a conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township exists as this study confirmed. The children in the study spoke about a range of abusive disciplinary methods used by parents. The most common form of discipline was physical abuse followed by verbal abuse which is an infringement on the part of child rights. Among adults what came out strongly are the deep-seated cultural beliefs that perpetuated physical and verbal abuse disciplinary practices and therefore, the parents feel the best way to discipline a child is through beatings against child rights.

The study described the actual conflict experienced between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in home institutions. The research study concluded that, children are used as tools of labor to advance family economic gain and yet, Child Rights Activists do not help them to fight the vices. It came out clearly that children are given extra home chores outside normal duties and chased away from homes. Among other revelation of the study includes: inhuman treatment, poverty and child neglect. Some of the children spoke of how they were physically assaulted by their elder relatives. This study in some instances, uncovered evidence of children who were beaten and left with marks on their bodies. This is a clear infringement of child rights.

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The study explored effects of the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township. The research study concluded that, hatred between children and their caregivers, marriage break ups, education and archaic uncontrolled behavior. Direct physical abuse is obvious, as is emotional effect that often manifests itself in behavioral, psychological and social problems. The effects from can be distressing to parents and children. Parents neglect and abandoned their children for fear of being taken to the police for prosecution in an event the child report them for child rights violations.

The study suggested the possible ways of how the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions in Mporokoso Township can be resolved. The study revealed that, there are no clear government policies that protect and fulfill children's rights and that child rights duty bearers are not doing enough to control child disciplinary practices in homes. Participants expressed concern on lack of child rights in general school curriculum and parent sensitization on the importance of human rights. Most of the participants said that, the conflict can be resolved by formulating policies and laws that promote, protect and fulfill child rights if the conflict is to be addressed and resolved. Overall, the study has brought to light the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in homes. The conflict is an epidemic that tortures and maims children. Child disciplinary practices in homes is one of the mostly pervasive child human rights violations denying children equality security, self-worth and their right to enjoy fundamental freedoms in Mporokoso Township.

Recommendations of the Study

Based on the findings and in line with the objectives, the following recommendations have been made and may be considered:

It was revealed in the study that the prevalence of conflict between child disciplinary practices and child human rights exists. The government should strive to provide clear policies and guideline on how children should be disciplined to avert beatings, verbal abuse and provide childhood social and security protection in order to fulfill their obligation.

- The government should regulate policies to reduce home chores disciplinary practices and stiff punishment for parents who used children as tools of labour to advance family economic gain, child neglect and abandonment. Child Rights Activists and other human rights organizations should help fight bad child disciplinary practices in family institutions.
- Direct physical abuse has emotional effect that often manifests itself in behavioural, psychological and social problems. Parents who abuse children should be taken to the police for prosecution.
- The government should collaborate with civil societies to educate the parents on child human rights and more especially include child rights education in the school curriculum as a subject of its own in order to reduce and possibly resolve the conflict between child disciplinary practices in family institutions and child human rights.
- The government should also initiate policies that are designed to promote and fulfill child right, harmonize child rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions.
- The government must also ensure wide public consultations before implementing child human rights. This enable the parents to be involved in the process, thereby addressing and resolving the conflict between child human rights and child disciplinary practices in family institutions.

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